

Human Resource And School-Based Management Implementation On Teaching Engagement In Central Schools

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Abstract: The study aimed to determine the level of the human resource management, implementation of School-Based Management (SBM) and engagement of 302 teachers in the selected central schools in the Division of Valencia City, Province of Bukidnon, Philippines. This further ascertains the relationship of human resource management and SBM implementation to teaching engagement and examines which of the variables, singly or in combination, best predicts the engagement of the teachers in central schools for School Year 2023-2024.

Descriptive analysis indicated that teachers experienced a high level of human resource management in the workplace. Meanwhile, the teachers described their School-Based Management (SBM) as fairly implemented. Furthermore, they are highly engaged as they practice their profession. Similarly, the findings revealed a significant relationship between human resource management and SBM implementation to teaching engagement. The predictors of teaching engagement are perceived organizational support, affective and normative commitment, discretionary behavior, curriculum and learning, and management of resources.

Keywords: *Organizational Support, Affective and Normative Commitment, Discretionary Behavior, Curriculum and Learning, Management Of Resources.*

Introduction

Education is a critical sector that must be prioritized to enhance a country's economic competitiveness [1]. For this reason, governments typically set aside a large chunk of their budget to raise educational standards. Moreover, teachers, being key players in education, have to be given adequate attention to improve teaching delivery. There is a need to provide enough help and support in order for them to carry out their duties efficiently. However, this conviction has been hampered by several circumstances that challenge teaching engagement constantly. This is influenced by various factors, one of which is the lack of teacher preparation in planning and readiness for the teaching and learning process. There are various contributing factors that hinder teaching engagement, such as being so preoccupied with paperwork that they sometimes neglect their most important job, which is to facilitate and supervise classroom instruction, and being busy with allocating resources to beautify their classrooms that they neglect their duties and responsibilities in giving the quality education to the school children [2].

In today's challenging economic landscape, many teachers struggle with financial strain, leading them to explore alternative sources of income, such as part-time business ventures and online selling. Moreover, in pursuit of better financial prospects, an increasing number of teachers in the Philippines are opting to seek employment opportunities abroad. This shift often stems from a perceived lack of engagement in their primary profession.

Additionally, since the onset of the pandemic in 2020, teachers have faced significant challenges in enhancing and updating their teaching skills due to limited access to professional development opportunities, largely driven by budget constraints within the

Department of Education. While training programs are occasionally made available, they are often restricted in scope and capacity, leaving many teachers without the opportunity to participate and engage fully. Research shows that inadequate and infrequent professional development can have a direct impact on teacher performance and student outcomes [3]. As a result, the competency gaps in students learning as reflected in the Division Achievement Test (DAT) results from August 2023, are a direct consequence of these limitations.

In consonance with the above reports, the National Achievement Test (NAT) result shows that Filipino learners are still far from the ideal mark, which is 75%. The national level percentage in the year 2017 was barely 39.95 for the Grade 6 overall MPS, which is described as very low mastery. In 2022, the Program for International Student Assessment (PISA) reported that in an international assessment, the students in the Philippines remain among the weakest, particularly in Math, Reading, and Science. The aforementioned condition posed a challenge to teachers as instructional leaders and major contributors to the productivity of the organization. The National Achievement Test (NAT) results and the standing of the Philippines in foreign evaluations are two obvious indicators that the entire educational system is still failing. As a result, it can be assumed that the majority of the country's public elementary schools have these gaps that need to be filled. Hence, it is required that every teacher participates and engages in activities that could help boost the performance level of students, consistent with the findings that teaching engagement is a determinant of the performance of students and is linked to their productivity [4].

The significant increase in student enrollment, particularly in public schools, has led to overcrowded classrooms, which severely

hinders the ability of teachers to deliver quality education; this issue further strained the capacity of the government to maintain educational standards and meet the growing demand for effective teaching. Such overcrowding not only affects the quality of instruction but also undermines the engagement of teachers and their ability to provide individualized attention [5]. In the context of the Division of Valencia City, the surge in enrollment during and after the pandemic poses a daunting challenge for teachers. Research indicates that high teacher-student ratios are associated with lower levels of teacher motivation, burnout, and job dissatisfaction, all of which affect the quality of education delivered [6].

Human resource management is important to the success of any organization because even with the best ideas, planning, and program implementation, an organization cannot function effectively if its degree of human resource management is inadequate. Human resource management plays a significant role in order to achieve the right degree of teaching engagement and efficiency at work. The instructional abilities of teachers, capacities, and competencies are being seriously tested by the management of organizations in an educational system. Improved teaching engagement, efficiency, and effectiveness must be pursued in order to thrive in today's increasingly competitive education market. The need for well-qualified, flexible, and proactive employees to assist schools in meeting their ever-increasing challenges of competitiveness, technological advancement, educational globalization, and improved teaching engagement has made employee training and development a critical human resource practice that no administrator can ignore in today's educational world. Human resource management is now central to employee utilization, commitment, motivation, and growth and is critical for increased teaching engagement.

On the other hand, school-based management gives schools more control in allocating and managing existing resources by enlisting the involvement and assistance of diverse stakeholders in the pursuit of quality education. It is considered one of the predicted factors that can improve teacher engagement. In response to the rapid increase in student enrollment, SBM has emerged to manage and improve educational quality, teacher engagement, and effectiveness at various levels [7].

This study examines how human resource and school-based management implementation affect teaching engagement in central schools of the Division of Valencia City for SY 2023-2024.

Materials and Methods

This study utilized the descriptive-correlational research design to determine the level of human resource management, School-Based Management implementation and teaching engagement of teachers in the Central Schools of the Division of Valencia City. The teaching engagement was the dependent variable while the independent variables of the study were human resource management and School-Based Management implementation.

The descriptive method was utilized to describe the three (3) aforementioned variables. On the other hand, correlation methods were applied to determine the relationship that exists between the human resource management and School-Based Management implementation to the teaching engagement. Multiple linear regression analysis was used to determine the predictors of the teaching engagement in the Central Schools of the Division of Valencia City.

The participants of the study consisted of three hundred two (302) public elementary school teachers. They are all assigned at different public Central Schools in the Division of Valencia City. To ensure that the teachers in each school are represented, total enumeration was used. Total enumeration refers to the inclusion of an entire population in the study, rather than using a sample. It aims to gather data from every individual or element within the defined population. The primary advantage of using this strategy is that it provides a complete and accurate representation of the entire population that eliminates sampling errors and ensures that the findings can be generalized to the entire group. Furthermore, it is particularly beneficial when dealing with smaller populations or when the cost and time constraints of sampling are not significant factors.

Part I of the questionnaire was on human resource management. This instrument comprised organizational support, attitude and behavior, affective and normative commitment, and discretionary behavior with five (5) items each. The questionnaire was adapted to suit the study [8]. This instrument was pilot tested to elementary teachers at Musuan Integrated School, Musuan Maramag Bukidnon and obtained a Cronbach's alpha of .861 indicating high reliability of the test items.

Part II of the questionnaire is on School-Based Management (SBM) implementation. This instrument was adapted from the study entitled School-Based Management Practices, Organizational Culture, and Adversity Quotient of Administrators: A Structural Model of Productivity [7]. There are four (4) indicators to be measured using the Three-Point Likert Scale. Indicator 1 was based on leadership and governance with five (5) items; indicator 2 on curriculum and learning with seven (7) items; indicator 3 dealt on accountability and continuous improvement with five (5) items; and indicator 4 about management of resources with five (5) items. The Cronbach's alpha of this questionnaire was .932 indicating high reliability of the test items.

Part III was on the teaching engagement. The instrument was adapted from the study on "Digital Proficiency and engagement on the technostress coping mechanism of basic education teachers" [10]. The key areas to be measured are the following. Job satisfaction, instructional design, classroom interaction, and work-life balance with five (8) items each. The Cronbach's alpha of this questionnaire was .969 indicating a high reliability of the test items.

The researcher was able to obtain a permit from the Institutional Ethics Review Committee (IERC) Office. This is to ensure compliance of the study to the ethical standards of conducting research. The researcher sought permission to conduct pilot testing at Musuan Integrated School, Division of Bukidnon. After complying with the permit, the researcher underwent pilot testing in the selected central schools in the Division of Bukidnon to test the reliability of the questionnaires that were accomplished by the respondents. The researcher sought permission from the Schools Division Superintendent of Valencia City Division to conduct the research through a letter request duly noted by the thesis adviser and the Dean of the College of Education of Central Mindanao University.

Upon approval of the Schools Division Superintendent, the school administrators in the selected central schools were informed through a letter that their teachers were chosen as the respondents of the study. The researcher encouraged the respondents to give their honest and precise answers to establish the reliability of the

findings. They were assured that the data they provided was kept confidential and was only used for the study.

The following rating scale was used to better understand the data:

Scale	Range	Descriptive Rating	Qualitative Interpretation
5	4.51-5.00	Outstanding (O)	Very Highly Managed
4	3.51-4.50	Very Satisfactory (VS)	Highly Managed
3	2.51-3.50	Satisfactory (S)	Moderately Managed
2	1.51-2.50	Unsatisfactory (U)	Less Managed
1	1.00-1.50	Poor (P)	Not Managed

Scale	Range	Descriptive Rating	Qualitative Interpretation
3	2.50- 3.00	Always (A)	Highly Implemented
2	1.50- 2.49	Occasionally (O)	Fairly Implemented
1	1.00-1.49	Seldom (S)	Poorly Implemented

Scale	Range	Descriptive Rating	Qualitative Interpretation
5	4.51-5.00	Outstanding (O)	Very Highly Engaged
4	3.51-4.50	Very Satisfactory (VS)	Highly Engaged
3	2.51-3.50	Satisfactory (S)	Moderately Engaged
2	1.51-2.50	Unsatisfactory (U)	Less Engaged
1	1.00-1.50	Poor (P)	Not Engaged

Results and Discussions

This section includes the presentation of the gathered data and comprehensive analysis, interpretation, support, and implication of the findings of the study.

➤ Summary of the Human Resource Management experienced by teachers in Central Schools.

Table 1. Summary of Human Resource Management experienced by teachers assigned in Central Schools.

INDICATORS	Mean	Descriptive Rating	Qualitative Interpretation
Attitudes and behavior	4.33	Very Satisfactory	Highly Managed
Organizational support	4.28	Very Satisfactory	Highly Managed
Discretionary behavior	4.26	Very Satisfactory	Highly Managed
Affective and normative commitment	4.19	Very Satisfactory	Highly Managed
Overall Mean	4.26	Very Satisfactory	Highly Managed

Legend:

Rating Scale	Descriptive Rating	Qualitative Interpretation
4.51-5.00	Outstanding (O)	Very Highly Managed
3.51-4.50	Very Satisfactory (VS)	Highly Managed
2.51-3.50	Satisfactory (S)	Moderately Managed
1.51-2.50	Unsatisfactory (U)	Less Managed
1.00-1.50	Poor (P)	Not Managed

Table 1 shows the summary of the teachers mean scores in human resource management. It is exposed that among the four variables used to measure the human resource management of the teachers assigned in central schools, the variable “attitudes and behavior” got a mean of 4.33, the variable “organizational support” got a mean of 4.28, the third indicator “discretionary behavior” got a mean of 4.26, and lastly, “affective and normative commitment” got a mean of 4.19. The overall mean of human resource management of the teachers assigned in central schools was 4.26, with a qualitative interpretation of highly managed.

The findings from Table 1 indicate that the human resource management for teachers in central schools are highly effective. Attitudes and Behavior with a mean of 4.33, which is the highest-rated variable, suggesting that teachers have a positive attitude towards their work environment, which likely fosters a collaborative and supportive culture. Positive attitudes can lead to increased job satisfaction and motivation. On the other hand, organizational support, with a mean of 4.28, indicates that teachers feel supported by their organization, which can enhance their engagement and commitment. This support likely encourages them to perform at their best and engage in human resource management. Moreover, discretionary behavior with a mean of 4.26 shows a significant level indicating that teachers are willing to go above and beyond their formal job requirements, such as helping colleagues and volunteering for additional responsibilities. This is a positive sign of a proactive workforce. Lastly, the affective and normative commitment has the lowest mean of 4.19 among the variables which still reflects a strong commitment among teachers. Affective commitment indicates emotional attachment to the school, while normative commitment reflects a sense of obligation to stay, both of which are crucial for retention and morale. Finally, the overall mean of 4.26 suggests that human resource management in these schools is highly managed. This implies that teachers feel well-supported, engaged, and committed, contributing to a positive and productive educational environment.

The results highlight a strong and effective approach to human resource management within central schools. The positive attitudes of the teacher, support, and willingness to engage in human resource management suggest a healthy organizational climate that can lead to improved student outcomes and teacher retention.

According to the study on “Affective Commitment and Normative Commitment Influences Turnover Intentions,” organizations that are less capable of managing human resources effectively have an impact on workers' desire to leave their jobs. A teacher's commitment to a school organization can have a significant impact

since it can improve the organization's quality, promote teamwork, develop a desire to make changes, and build a worker's relationship with his or her organization [11].

In another insight, the study on “Leadership Development in Higher Education,” a literature review and implications for program redesign, in times of increasingly restricted financial and human resources, school administrators face additional challenges in equity managing their units and ensuring that programs and employees are sufficiently supported [12]. As a result, administrators face increased demands for expertise in all elements of their job responsibilities, while the problems they face become increasingly severe. According to the report, school leaders should actively participate in professional networks within and across schools to enhance knowledge, skills, and practices.

Furthermore, another study assert that institutions need to restructure and reorient towards human resource development as the key driver for value creation to effectively confront intensifying competition at national, regional, and global levels [13].

➤ **Summary of the School-Based Management Implementation observed by teachers in Central Schools.**

Table 2. Summary of the Mean Scores of School-Based Management Implementation observed by teachers in Central Schools.

INDICATORS	Mean	Descriptive Rating	Qualitative Interpretation
Curriculum and Learning	2.42	Occasionally (O)	Fairly Implemented
Accountability and Continuous Improvement	2.42	Occasionally (O)	Fairly Implemented
Leadership and Governance	2.40	Occasionally (O)	Fairly Implemented
Management of Resources	2.40	Occasionally (O)	Fairly Implemented
Overall Mean	2.41	Occasionally (O)	Fairly Implemented

Legend:

Rating Scale	Descriptive Rating	Qualitative Interpretation
2.50-3.00	Always(A)	Highly Implemented
1.50-2.49	Occasionally (O)	Fairly Implemented
1.00-1.49	Seldom (S)	Poorly Implemented

Table 2 shows the summary of the mean scores of school-based management implementation observed by teachers in central schools. It shows that among the four variables used to measure the school-based management implementation of the elementary teachers assigned in central schools, the variable “curriculum and learning” got the highest mean of 2.42, while the variable

“accountability and continuous improvement” got a mean of 2.42. Moreover, the variable “leadership and governance” got a mean of 2.40. Lastly, the variable “management of resources” got the lowest mean of 2.40. Furthermore, the results show that the public elementary school teachers assigned in central schools in Valencia City Division are at the maturing level of school-based management implementation as measured in the overall mean of 2.41.

The results indicate that the implementation of school-based management among public elementary school teachers in central schools in the Division of Valencia City is fairly implemented. This result suggests that the teachers are becoming more adept and effective in applying the principles of school-based management. The variables “curriculum and learning” and “accountability and continuous improvement” both got a mean of 2.42, the highest mean score among the four variables, indicating that teachers feel relatively confident and capable in this area, which is crucial for student achievement. Furthermore, “accountability and continuous improvement” show that teachers are committed to improving their practices and holding themselves accountable. Moreover, “leadership and governance” with a mean of 2.40 shows a moderate level of implementation, suggesting that while there is some effective leadership and governance, there may be room for enhancement in these areas, and lastly, “management of resources” with a mean of 2.40 got the lowest mean, which indicates that managing resources effectively is a challenge, suggesting a potential area for focus and improvement.

The mean score of 2.41 reflects a solid foundation of school-based management implementation, with specific strengths in curriculum and accountability, but also highlights the need for continued growth in leadership and resource management.

School administrators shared decisions, and common understanding was formed through broad involvement activities, including teachers, students, and parents [14]. Knowledge was institutionalized. Institution leaders also mentioned that they are attempting to make learning permanent for the institution by fostering a powerful corporate culture.

The school community is actively engaged in the development and implementation of school plans matched with institutional goals and policies [15]. The SBM can: first, improve the learning outcomes of students; second, improve the teaching-learning environment [16]; third, increase administrative efficiency and tighten professional control [17]; fourth, increase parental involvement fifth, enhance school commitment [16]; and lastly, enhance accountability, satisfaction and performance of teachers [18].

➤ **Summary of the Teaching Engagement Observed by Teachers in Central Schools.**

Table 3. Summary of Teaching Engagement of Teachers

INDICATORS	Mean	Descriptive Rating	Qualitative Interpretation
Classroom interaction	4.55	Outstanding	Very Highly Engaged
Job satisfaction	4.51	Outstanding	Very Highly Engaged
Instructional design	4.47	Very Satisfactorily	Highly Engaged

Work-life balance	4.34	Very Satisfactorily	Highly Engaged
Overall Mean	4.46	Very satisfactory	Highly Engaged

Legend:

Rating Scale	Descriptive Rating	Qualitative Interpretation
4.51-5.00	Outstanding (O)	Very Highly Engaged
3.51-4.50	Very Satisfactory (VS)	Highly Engaged
2.51-3.50	Satisfactory (S)	Moderately Engaged
1.51-2.50	Unsatisfactory (U)	Less Engaged
1.00-1.50	Poor (P)	Not Engaged

Table 3 shows the summary of the mean scores of teaching engagement of the teachers assigned in central schools. It is exposed that among the four (4) variables used to measure the teaching engagement of teachers, the variable “classroom interaction” got a mean of 4.55. The second variable, “job satisfaction,” got a mean of 4.51, while the third variable, “instructional design,” got a mean of 4.47. Further, the variable “work-life balance” got a mean of 4.34; all indicators mentioned above are interpreted as “highly engaged.”

In addition, the public elementary school teachers’ level of teaching engagement got an overall mean of 4.46, which indicates that the teachers are highly engaged. Table 16 shows the mean scores of teaching engagement among teachers assigned in central schools.

The findings reveal that teachers exhibit a high level of engagement across all variables measured: The variable “classroom interaction,” with a mean of 4.55 as the highest mean, indicates that teachers are very actively engaged in fostering positive and respectful relationships with their students and managing classroom dynamics effectively. This engagement is crucial for creating a supportive learning environment.

Furthermore, “job satisfaction,” with a mean of 4.51, reflects a positive feeling of teachers about their work, suggesting they find fulfillment and pride in their roles. High job satisfaction is often linked to better performance and retention. Moreover, “instructional design,” with a mean of 4.47, indicates that teachers are committed to developing effective instructional strategies and integrating technology, which is essential for enhancing student learning outcomes. At the same time, “work-life balance” got a mean of 4.34. Although these two variables have the lowest score among the four variables, it still indicates a very high level of engagement. Teachers generally feel they can manage their professional and personal lives effectively, though there may be areas for improvement.

The overall mean score for teaching engagement of 4.46 indicates that teachers are very highly engaged in their teaching practices. This overall engagement is significant as it suggests a positive teaching environment where teachers are motivated and actively involved in their work, which can lead to better student outcomes.

The findings suggest that public elementary school teachers in central schools are highly engaged across various aspects of their professional roles. This level of engagement is likely to foster a positive educational experience for both teachers and students. However, the slightly lower score in work-life balance indicates that while teachers feel engaged, there may be opportunities to further enhance their well-being in this area.

Based on the findings of the study on teachers’ commitment and self-efficacy as predictors of work engagement and well-being, teachers become more involved in their work and are more devoted to their students [19]. Academic institutions can increase the likelihood of educators becoming involved in their work if they can help them become more devoted. In order to secure more engaged educators, schools must support educators' commitment. This review can help teachers become more aware of how their high levels of well-being will enable them to be more engaged, successful, and capable of handling obstacles as they arise within their instructional process.

The results of the study of a researcher may also guide organizational initiatives that promote employee motivation, productivity, engagement, and retention during and even beyond the COVID-19 pandemic. This study's findings revealed how showing care and concern toward employees engenders performance and commitment [20].

In addition, posited that engaged teachers are motivated enough to demonstrate vigor and productivity to complete tasks, and they can also handle many difficulties of daily life [19]. Teaching engagement is an autonomously managed form of motivation that has been demonstrated to result in a better presentation, tenacity, and teacher creativity. Teachers who are not fully engaged in their lessons are more likely to feel in control of their environment and to be motivated by rewards rather than punishment. Various forms of engagement exist, including cognitive engagement, which suggests an activity that is completed with attention, immersion, and focus while maintaining an imperceptible sense of time. Emotionally charged engagement is defined as fondness, delight, pleasure, thrill, and entertainment related to teaching.

➤ ***Correlation Analysis of the Human Resource Management and School-Based Management Implementation to Teaching Engagement.***

Table 4. Correlation Analysis of the Variables

Independent Variables Correlated with Teachers’ Teaching Engagement	Correlation Coefficient (r)	P-value
Human Resource Management	.414	.000**
Organizational support	.263	.000**
Attitude and behavior	.158	.006**
Affective and normative commitment	.266	.000**
Discretionary behavior	.425	.000**
School-Based Management Implementation	.323	.000**
Leadership and Governance	.255	.000**
Curriculum and Learning	.234	.000**

Accountability and Continuous Improvement	.198	.001**
Management of Resources	.304	.000**

**Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)

*Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed)

Ns not significant

As shown in table 4, correlation results indicated that the human resource management and its sub-components, particularly organizational support $r=0.263$, ($p<0.01$), attitudes and behavior $r=0.158$, ($p>0.01$), affective and normative commitment $r=0.266$, ($p<0.01$), discretionary behavior $r=0.425$, ($p<0.01$) showed statistical significance relative to the teaching engagement of teachers assigned in central schools.

This is to say that the positive results of teachers' human resource management in terms of organizational support, employer attitudes and behavior, affective and normative commitment, and discretionary behavior lead to a positive teaching engagement of teachers. This also means that the more human resource management the teachers have, the more engaged they are with their work.

According to the study on the "Impact of HRM Practices on Teacher Engagement and Performance: A Systematic Review," organizational support (OS) has a direct impact on teacher engagement, which aligns with the findings ($r = 1$, $p < 0.01$). The findings reinforced that OS boosts teachers' emotional attachment to their work and institution, resulting in higher levels of engagement [21]. Moreover, attitudes and behaviors such as job satisfaction and trust in leadership were strongly correlated with teachers' discretionary behaviors, consistent with the findings ($r = 0.425$, $p < 0.01$).

Furthermore, the study on the "Role of Affective Commitment and Organizational Support in Enhancing Teacher Engagement" examined how HRM practices, particularly affective commitment and organizational support, influence teacher engagement in primary and secondary schools. They found that HRM practices that promote emotional attachment to the organization and enhanced organizational support were positively correlated with teacher engagement [22]. Teachers who felt supported by their administrators showed higher levels of emotional attachment (affective commitment) and were likelier to display engaged classroom behaviors. The study supports the findings regarding the importance of affective commitment ($r = 0.266$, $p < 0.01$) and organizational support in promoting teacher engagement. It highlights that when teachers perceive their institution as caring and supportive, their commitment to the organization increases, thereby enhancing their teaching engagement [22].

As shown, the degree of correlations was generally moderately high in variables leadership and governance and management of resources, it entails that the increase of school-based management implementation will lead to an increase of teaching engagement of teachers which means that teachers are highly engaged in terms of school-based management implementation in the workplace, more likely they will be engaged with their work. However, the decrease in school-based management leads to a decrease of teachers teaching engagement which means that teachers are not engaged in school-based management implementation in the workplace.

According to the study on "The Impact of School-Based Management on Teacher Engagement and Professional

Development in Malaysia." This study explores the effect of SBM implementation on teacher engagement and professional growth. It found that SBM practices significantly improve teacher engagement and motivation, particularly in leadership and resource management. It revealed that the involvement of teachers in decision-making processes, as a part of SBM, increased their sense of ownership and responsibility toward their teaching duties [23].

Furthermore, the study conducted on "School Leadership and Governance: Key Drivers of Teacher Engagement" explored how school leadership and governance directly influenced teacher engagement. Results suggested that schools with clear governance structures and empowered school leaders were better able to create environments conducive to high teacher engagement. A strong leader who effectively communicated goals and expectations was found to be critical for sustaining SBM initiatives [24].

Thus, the null hypothesis, which argues that there is no significant relationship between teacher engagement and human resource management and school-based management implementation, is rejected. This means that teacher engagement is related in some manner to human resource management and school-based management implementation.

➤ Regression Analysis of the Variables.

Regression generally allows this study to explain and examine the relationship between predictor variables and a dependent or criterion variable. As such, predictor variables included in the research were: a) human resource management which includes dimensions such as organizational support, employee attitudes and behavior, affective and normative commitment, and discretionary behavior; b) school-based management implementation, which consisted of the order factors: leadership and governance, curriculum and learning, accountability and continuous improvement, and management of resources. Multiple regression analysis would observe the extent of influence of the predictor variables on the criterion variable, the teaching engagement.

Table 5. A regression analysis on Human Resource Management and School-Based Management to Teaching Engagement.

INDICATORS	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	2.043	.196		10.403	.000
Human Resource Management					
Discretionary Behavior	.198	.039	.274	5.128	.000
Organizational Support	.107	.034	.153	3.183	.002
Affective and Normative Commitment	.087	.031	.143	2.771	.006

School-Based Management Implementation					
Curriculum and Learning	.186	.046	.220	4.069	.000
Management of Resources	.132	.043	.175	3.100	.002
R=0.613	R ² =0.376	F=35.686		Sig.0.000	

Table 5 gives information about the regression model of the study, estimating the impact of various simultaneous influences upon a single dependent variable. Clearly, teachers' teaching engagement was affected by human resource management in terms of organizational support $\beta = .153$, $t (3.183)$, $p < 0.002$, affective and normative commitment $\beta = .143$, $t (2.771)$, $p < 0.006$, and discretionary behavior $\beta = .274$, $t (5.128)$, $p < 0.000$ also, the variable school-based management in terms of curriculum and learning $\beta = .220$, $t (4.069)$, $p < 0.000$, and management of resources $\beta = .175$, $t (3.100)$, $p < 0.002$ can predict the teaching engagement of teachers.

More precisely, the predicted scores for values of the independent variables are indicated by the beta weights (β), which means that each additional score/unit accounted for by human resource management in terms of organizational support, affective and normative commitment, and discretionary behavior would imply an increase on teaching engagement of teachers, holding other variable constants. Consequently, this suggests that if the teachers manage human resource management in terms of organizational support, affective and normative commitment, and discretionary behavior, their teaching engagement will also be better. In addition, each additional score/unit accounted by school-based management of teachers in terms of curriculum and learning and management of resources would suggest an increase in teaching engagement of teachers, holding other variables constant.

The R² measured the total variation of the dependent variable, which constituted 37.6%, reflected the total amount of variance explained by Organizational Support_HRM, Affective and Normative Commitment_HRM, Discretionary Behavior_HRM, Curriculum and Learning_SBM, Management of Resources_SBM. In contrast, 62.4% could be attributed to other factor variables outside the regression model. From the preceding analysis, the equation could be used in predicting the engagement of teachers (Y) as indicated by the F-Value (35.686) with its corresponding probability ($p=0.000$) was significant at $P < 0.01$.

The study suggests that there is a relationship between the independent variables of human resource management (organizational support), human resource management (affective and normative commitment), human resource management (discretionary behavior), school-based management (curriculum and learning), school-based management (management of resources) and the dependent variable of the teaching engagement of teachers. The findings indicate that these independent variables are positively associated with teaching engagement, suggesting that teachers with higher levels of human resource management and school-based management implementation tend to engage better in

their work. Thus, the null hypothesis, stating that there is no variable that best predicts the teaching engagement of the teachers, is rejected.

The implication of these findings is that investing in programs and initiatives that support the development of human resource management and school-based management implementation among teachers can have significant benefits in improving their teaching engagement. By providing training and resources for teachers to develop their school-based management skills, schools can help them to effectively integrate their learnings and skills from training into their teaching practices, promote innovation, and enhance the quality of instruction. Additionally, promoting human resource management in the workplace can help enhance teacher resilience and adaptability, contributing to their overall teaching engagement.

The study on "Role of HRM in Enhancing Teacher Engagement: The Influence of Organizational Support and Commitment" examined the relationship between HRM practices, specifically, perceived organizational support and affective commitment and teacher engagement across different educational systems. The authors found that organizational support and affective commitment were positively correlated with teacher engagement. The study suggests that a supportive work environment and fostering emotional attachment are crucial in improving teacher engagement, particularly when teachers are given adequate resources and recognition. The result further emphasizes this relationship, demonstrating that HRM practices encouraging support significantly predict teacher engagement [25].

Moreover, in the study on "School Leadership and Teacher Engagement: Mediating Role of Organizational Support," investigated how school leadership, as part of the broader HRM framework, influenced teacher engagement through the mediating role of organizational support. The study found that effective school leadership practices, such as providing adequate support and resources, were associated with higher teacher engagement. Teachers who perceived their leaders as supportive were more committed to their roles and more engaged in teaching activities. The study highlighted that both perceived organizational support and school leadership were essential in enhancing teacher engagement [26].

The findings from these studies provide a robust foundation for your research on the interconnectedness of human resource management, school-based management, and teaching engagement. They highlight the importance of supportive HRM practices and effective management strategies in fostering a positive teaching environment, ultimately leading to higher levels of engagement among teachers. By investing in these areas, educational institutions can enhance teacher commitment and effectiveness, contributing to improved educational outcomes.

Conclusions and Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn:

The results indicate that teachers in central schools experienced human resource management as highly effective, with key variables such as Attitudes and Behavior, Organizational Support, and Discretionary Behavior receiving strong ratings. These factors contribute to a positive work environment, increased engagement, and a proactive workforce. While Affective and Normative

Commitment was the lowest-rated variable, it still reflects a strong sense of emotional attachment and obligation, which are important for retention. The high ratings suggest that effective human resource management plays a significant role in fostering a supportive, motivated, and productive teaching environment.

The study revealed that school-based management in central schools is fairly implemented, with notable strengths in Curriculum and Learning, Accountability and Continuous Improvement, Leadership and Governance, and Management of Resources, highlighting opportunities for growth. Furthermore, teachers in central schools practiced a high level of engagement across key areas, including Classroom Interaction, Job Satisfaction, Instructional Design, and Work-Life Balance. The strong ratings in Classroom Interaction, Job Satisfaction, and Instructional Design reflect the active involvement of teachers, commitment to effective teaching practices, and pride in their roles. Although the lowest-rated variable, Work-life Balance, still indicates strong engagement with some potential for improvement. The high mean score of 4.47 suggests that teachers are highly engaged, fostering a positive teaching environment that is likely to enhance student outcomes.

Moreover, the study found a significant positive relationship between human resource management, school-based management, and teaching engagement. Both human resource and school-based management factors strongly influence teaching engagement. Regression analysis identified perceived organizational support, affective and normative commitment, and discretionary behavior (human resource management), while curriculum and learning and management of resources (school-based management) were key predictors. The model explained 37.6% of the variance, suggesting other factors may also impact teaching engagement. Thus, the null hypothesis is rejected, confirming that human resources and school-based management are vital for enhancing teaching engagement.

Based on the findings of the study, the following are the recommendations:

School administrators may continue to leverage and enhance the strengths of human resource management in central schools by maintaining a positive and supportive environment, implementing programs that recognize teachers' efforts, providing necessary resources, offering emotional and professional support, and empowering teachers to take initiative in their roles and make decisions that improve teaching and learning outcomes.

External stakeholders may play a key role by providing targeted support and resources aimed at strengthening leadership capacity and improving resource management within schools. These programs could offer professional development for school leaders, facilitate access to best practices in governance, and ensure that schools are equipped with the necessary resources to support their initiatives effectively.

Teachers in central schools may continue to build on their strengths in Classroom Interaction, Job Satisfaction, and Instructional Design, which reflect their high levels of engagement, commitment to effective teaching, and pride in their work by exploring strategies for better managing their workload and personal time, such as collaborating with colleagues to share best practices for efficiency, utilizing support resources available through the school, or participating in professional development focused on stress management and time management skills.

Moreover, parents play a key role by promoting collaboration and open communication with school administrators and teachers. Parents may encourage school leaders to prioritize strengthening human resource management by ensuring that teachers feel supported, empowered, and committed. Additionally, parents can advocate for the continued development of school-based management, particularly in areas such as discretionary behavior and resource management. Since these areas have the highest variable scores, enhancing them can directly improve teaching effectiveness and, in turn, foster greater teacher engagement.

Educational institutions may offer targeted professional development opportunities to enhance teachers' discretionary behavior within human resource management (HRM) and improve curriculum and learning management within school-based management (SBM). Workshops and training sessions can be designed to foster proactive behaviors, empower teachers, and strengthen their ability to go beyond basic job requirements. Additionally, professional development should address the improvement of curriculum design and teaching strategies to further elevate engagement. Furthermore, incorporating the evaluation of teachers' HRM and SBM skills, particularly in discretionary behavior and curriculum implementation, into the appraisal process will provide valuable feedback and support, helping teachers refine these key areas and ultimately improve teaching and learning outcomes.

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